

A Novel Synthesis of 2-Amino-4-5-disubstituted-thiazole and 2-Amino-5-hydro-4-arylo-6-arylthiazolo[5,4-c]-pyridazin-5-ones and their Biological Properties†

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Ethyl γ -bromo- α -arylo-azetoacetates (1) were reacted with thiourea in DMF to give the corresponding ethyl 2-amino- α -arylo-4-thiazolylacetates (2), which when coupled with arene diazonium chloride in presence of sodium acetate, gave the corresponding ethyl 2-amino- α -arylo-5-(arylo)-4-thiazolylacetates (3-5). The thiazoles (3-5) when cyclised in presence of a base afforded the 2-amino-4-arylo-6-arylthiazolo[5,4-c]-pyridazin-5-ones (6-8). The compounds were tested for biological properties.

THE use of thiazole in curative treatment has been firmly established¹. Several thiazole derivatives were found to be clinically useful for the treatment of bacterial, protozoal and helminthic disorders^{2,3}. In view of the above, it was considered of interest to synthesise some new thiazole derivatives and thiazolo[5,4-c]pyridazinones, and to evaluate their biological properties. Very few unambiguous syntheses of thiazolo[5,4-c]pyridazinone system are reported in literature^{4,5}. In the light of this it has been considered worthwhile to explore a facile synthesis of thiazolo[5,4-c]pyridazinone from the appropriate aminothiazole.

A survey of literature reveals that thiazolo[5,4-c]pyridazine system has been synthesised by the reaction of 5-hydroxy-2-substituted-4-thiazolylmethyl ketone with hydrazine⁴ and also by the reaction of substituted-4-amino-3-mercaptopyridazine with cyanogen bromide⁵. We report herein a novel synthesis of 2-amino-4-arylo-6-arylthiazolo[5,4-c]pyridazin-5-one by an entirely different route. The reaction of γ -bromoarylo-azetoacetates^{6,7}, obtained by the bromination of ethyl arylo-azetoacetates^{8,9}, with thiourea in DMF at reflux temperature for 2-3 h, gave the desired ethyl 2-amino- α -arylo-4-thiazolyl acetates (2) in good yield¹⁰. Compound 2 also exists in its tautomeric form 2-amino- α -arylo-4-hydroxy-4-thiazolyl acetate, which was supported by ir spectra in solid state, while pmr showed hydrazone structure (2).

2-Aminothiazoles (2) when coupled with arene diazonium salt in dioxan-ethanol and sodium acetate, gave the desired product 2-amino-5-arylo-4-thiazolyl acetates (3-5). The coupling takes place at C-5 of thiazole ring^{11,12} under this condition and not at α -C to give formazan¹³, as it requires more basic

condition. The structure of the substituted-thiazoles(3-5) was confirmed by ir bands at 3 100-3 300 (NH), 1 730 (ester C=O) and 1 610-1 615 cm^{-1} (N=N), and further supported by pmr spectra which exhibited broad signal of one-proton intensity at δ 13.3-13.9 ascribed to NH proton (exchangeable). This indicates that coupling does not occur at α -C. Further, the disappearance of shielded thiazole proton at δ 6.8 supports the coupl-

- a ; Ph = 4-Bromophenyl 3 ; Ar = Phenyl
b ; Ph = 4-Nitrophenyl 4 ; Ar = 4-Nitrophenyl
c ; Ph = 2,4,6-Tribromophenyl 5 ; Ar = 2,4,6-Tribromophenyl
6 ; Ar = Phenyl
7 ; Ar = 4-Nitrophenyl
8 ; Ar = 2,4,6-Tribromophenyl
Scheme 1

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ing at C-5 of the thiazole (2). Other signals were in agreement with this coupled product.

Cyclisation of 2-amino-4,5-disubstituted-thiazole (3-5) in the presence of a base like sodium acetate, pyridine, piperidine, morpholine and triethylamine in ethanol at reflux temperature for 4-5 h, gave the corresponding 2-amino-4-arylo-6-arylthiazolo-[5,4-c]pyridazin-5-ones (6-8) in good yield. The probable mechanism in the presence of a base is explained in Scheme 1. The lone-pair of electrons on S and N can be delocalised over N=N, which can intermolecularly attack the ester group with the elimination of EtOH, resulting in the formation of 6-8. The structures of 6-8 were established by ir and pmr spectral data.

Biological activity: Some of the compounds (3-8) were tested for their antibacterial activity *in vitro* against the microorganisms *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* in nutrient agar media following the Kirby-Bauer filter paper-disc method¹⁴. Some of the compounds (3, 5) were found to be significantly active against the organisms.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in an open capillary and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 or 60 MHz) spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard.

Ethyl 2-amino- α -arylo-4-thiazolylacetates (2): To a solution of ethyl γ -bromoaryloacetates (1) (0.01 mol) in DMF (20 ml), was added a solution of thiourea (0.011 mol) in DMF (10 ml) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 2-3 h. After cooling it was then poured into ice-water, and the resulting solid (2) was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from DMF to yield 2 (Table 1): 2a (Ph=4-bromophenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O), 3100-3300br (NH) and 1595 cm^{-1} (N=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.15-4.3 (2H, q, J 8 Hz, COOCH₂), 1.0-1.3 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 6.8 (1H, s, H-5), 13.3-13.9 (1H, br, NH exchangeable), 5.1-5.3 (2H, br, NH₂) and 7.25-7.45 (4H, m, ArH); 2b (Ph=4-nitrophenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O), 3100-3280br (NH), 1610 (N=N) and 1580 cm^{-1} (NO₂); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.1-4.3 (2H, q, J 8 Hz, COOCH₂), 1.1-1.35 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 6.82 (1H, s, H-5), 13.1-13.8 (1H, br, NH exchangeable), 5.0-5.3 (2H, br, NH₂) and 7.3-7.4 (4H, m, ArH); 2c (Ph=2,4,6-tribromophenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O), 3100-3300 (NH) and 1600 cm^{-1} (N=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.15-4.3 (2H, q, J 8 Hz, COOCH₂), 1.0-1.35 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 6.8 (1H, s, H-5), 13.1-13.9 (1H, br, NH exchangeable), 5.15-5.3 (2H, br, NH₂) and 7.3-7.4 (2H, m, ArH).

TABLE I - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no	Ph	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
2a	4-Bromophenyl	220	78	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ SBr
2b	4-Nitrophenyl	245	82	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S
2c	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	202	76	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ SBr ₃
Ar = Phenyl				
3a	4-Bromophenyl	246	81	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₂ SBr
3b	4-Nitrophenyl	226	80	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₄ S
3c	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	152	73	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ SBr ₃
Ar = 4-Nitrophenyl				
4a	4-Bromophenyl	216	83	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₇ O ₄ SBr
4b	4-Nitrophenyl	256	76	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₇ O ₆ S
4c	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	241	71	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₇ O ₄ SBr ₃
Ar = 2,4,6-Tribromophenyl				
5a	4-Bromophenyl	232	80	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ SBr ₄
5b	4-Nitrophenyl	268	76	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₇ O ₄ SBr ₃
5c	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	239	69	C ₁₀ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ SBr ₄
Ar = Phenyl				
6a	4-Bromophenyl	211	84	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₆ OSBr
6b	4-Nitrophenyl	232	78	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₇ O ₂ S
6c	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	219	77	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₆ OSBr ₃
Ar = 4-Nitrophenyl				
7a	4-Bromophenyl	298	63	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₇ O ₂ SBr
7b	4-Nitrophenyl	279	61	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₈ O ₂ S
7c	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	288	65	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₇ O ₂ SBr ₃
Ar = 2,4,6-Tribromophenyl				
8a	4-Bromophenyl	271	67	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₆ OSBr ₄
8b	4-Nitrophenyl	278	73	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₇ O ₂ SBr ₃
8c	2,4,6-Tribromophenyl	259	64	C ₁₇ H ₈ N ₆ OSBr ₄

Ethyl 2-amino- α -[arylo]-5-[arylo]-4-thiazolyl acetates (3-5) General procedure: Sodium nitrite (0.021 mol) dissolved in water (25 ml), was gradually added to a well-cooled solution of aromatic amine (0.02 mol) in 3 N HCl (2.5 ml) with stirring. The diazonium salt solution was then filtered into a cold suspension of 2 (0.02 mol) and sodium acetate (10 gm) in ethanol-dioxan (4:1; 50 ml) with stirring at 0-5° for 1 h. After 3 h, the solid was filtered, washed several times with water and recrystallised from DMF-ethanol (1:2) to yield 3-(Table 1): 3a (Ph=4-bromophenyl; Ar=phenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O), 3100-3300br (NH) and 1605 cm^{-1} (N=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.14-4.3 (2H, q, COOCH₂), 1.0-1.3 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 13.3-13.7 (1H, br, NH exchangeable), 5.1-5.35 (2H, br, NH₂) and 7.27-7.78 (9H, m, 2 x ArH); 4a (Ph=4-bromophenyl; Ar=4-nitrophenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O), 3100-3260 br (NH), 1615 (N=N) and 1580 cm^{-1} (NO₂); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.1-4.3 (2H, q, COOCH₂), 1.1-1.3 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 13.1-13.8 (1H, br, NH exchangeable), 5.15-5.35 (2H, br, NH₂) and 7.3-7.75 (8H, m, 2 x ArH); 5a (Ph=4-bromophenyl; Ar=2,4,6-tribromophenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 1730 (ester C=O), 3100-3300br (NH) and 1610 cm^{-1} (N=N); δ (DMSO- d_6) 4.15-4.35 (2H, q, COOCH₂), 1.15-1.3 (3H, t, J 8 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 13.2-13.75 (1H, br, NH

exchangeable), 5.1–5.3 (2H, br, NH₂) and 7.3–7.67 (6H, m, 2 × ArH).

The spectra of other compounds (3b, c, 4b, c, 5b, c) exhibited satisfactory results.

2-Amino-4-[arylo]-6-arylthiazolo[5,4-c]pyridazin-5-one (6–8). *General procedure*: A solution of 3–5 (0.01 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed in presence of triethylamine (2 ml) [in place of triethylamine, pyridine, piperidine, morpholine and sodium acetate were also used and gave the same products] for 3 h. On cooling the reaction mixture, the resulting solid was filtered, washed with cold ethanol, dried and crystallised from ethanol to yield 6–8 (Table 1): 6a (Ph=4-bromophenyl; Ar=phenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 3 100–3 200br (NH), 1 680 (ring C=O) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (N=N); δ (CDCl₃) 5.1–5.3 (2H, br, NH₂ exchangeable with D₂O) and 7.23–7.8 (9H, m, 2 × ArH); 7a (Ph=4-bromophenyl; Ar=4-nitrophenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 3 100–3 250br (NH), 1 680 (ring C=O), 1 615 (N=N) and 1 585 cm⁻¹ (NO₂); δ (DMSO-d₆) 5.15–5.3 (2H, br, NH₂, D₂O exchangeable) and 7.3–7.75 (8H, m, 2 × ArH); 8c (Ph=2,4,6-tribromophenyl; Ar=2,4,6-tribromophenyl): ν_{max} (KBr) 3 100–3 280br (NH), 1 680 (ring C=O) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (N=N); δ (CDCl₃) 5.1–5.3 (2H, br, NH₂, D₂O exchangeable) and 7.3–7.45 (4H, m, 2 × ArH).

Spectra of other compounds (6b, c, 7b, c, 8b, c) exhibited satisfactory results.

The elemental analyses of all compounds were found satisfactory.

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